

Satellite Meeting on Complex Behaviour in Discrete Dynamical Systems

Mini-proceedings

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Foreword

The second edition of the 'Satellite Meeting on Complex Behaviour in Discrete Dynamical Systems' has attracted researchers from several institutions across the world. All together, eight submissions were selected for an oral presentation during the course of this meeting. Although this satellite meeting lasts only one afternoon, I hope that it is appreciated by its attendees and that it may serve as an ideal networking event.

On behalf of the organizing committee,
Jan M. Baetens,
Chair

Symposium Organization

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Lyapunov exponent: Towards randomness measure

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Abstract

We propose a method based on Lyapunov Exponent (LE) capable of measuring randomness of PRNG (Pseudo-random number generator). We study PRNG as a discrete dynamical system, motivated by the strong relation between chaos and randomness. Results show good discrimination among PRNG parameters.

Introduction

PRNG is an essential tool for stochastic methods like genetic algorithms and Monte Carlo methods, which are applied in science research and simulation studies to solve problems from different fields: physics, chemistry, biology, mathematics, etc. Despite its importance, the measure of PRNG randomness quality is still a serious difficulty. In particular, statistical tests remain inconclusive to measure randomness, since most of them measure the sequence distribution while ignoring randomness in timeline.

We propose a method capable of measuring PRNG randomness, inspired in the strong relationship between chaos and randomness (Machicao et al., 2012b). The LE is a measure to calculate “chaos” of dynamical systems by studying the rate of separation of close trajectories. Previous works showed good results in cryptography based on discrete LE (Machicao et al., 2012a). In this article, we employed the Linear congruential generator (LCG)—which remains the most popular PRNG—denoted as a modular integer recursion: $Y_{n+1} = (A \times Y_n + B) \bmod C$, where A, B and C are constants. We discuss the LCG randomness over particular values of the multiplier, the additive constant and the modulus.

Methods

We study the LCG as a discrete dynamical system based on Baetens's terms (Baetens and De Baets, 2010). To follow the dynamical evolution of two trajectories we employ the damage spread theory. Therefore, we handle each element (a bit) inside the LCG due to its topological sensitivity (Baetens and De Baets, 2010; Benatti et al., 2006).

Let S a set of N bits, $S_i = \{0, 1\}$, with function $s : S \rightarrow S$ that maps each bit c_i at time t , i.e., $s(c_i, t)$, which evolve according to LCG, $Y^s(t+1) = (A \times Y^s(t) + B) \bmod C$. Where, $Y^s(t) = \sum_{i=1}^N 2^{8(i-1)} s(c_i, t)$ is the integer value of s at t . To estimate the LE we considered two trajectories with close initial conditions, $s_0 = s(\cdot, 0)$ and $s_0^* = s^*(\cdot, 0)$, moreover with $Y^s(0)$ and $Y^{s^*}(0)$ respectively. We define a damage vector (DV): $h(\cdot, t) = s(\cdot, t) \oplus s^*(\cdot, t)$, where $\oplus$ is the mod 2 operator. This DV has to track all flipped bits as follow:

1. At $t = 0$: Given c_i the rightmost bit, such that $\sum_{c_i} h(c_i, 0) = 1$,
2. At $t = 1$: Lets evolve $Y^s(1)$, as well as $Y^{s^*}(1)$. Such that, $h(\cdot, 1)$ takes one when $s^*(c_j, 1) \neq s(c_j, 1)$, otherwise takes zero,
3. For every c_j for which $h(c_j, 1) = 1$, create a replica r^j containing the Boolean complement of $s(c_j, 1)$, such that $r^j(c_j, 1) = \bar{s}(c_j, 1)$.
4. When $t = 2$: Lets evolve $Y(2)$ and calculate $Y^*(2)$ for each of the replicas r^j , such that $Y^{r^j}(2) = (A \times Y^{r^j}(1) + B) \bmod C$. Where $h(c_j, 2) = \sum_{r^j} \sum_{c_i} h(c_i, 1)$, containing the sum of flipped bits of every r^j .
5. For every c_j and $Y^{r^j}(1)$ for which $r(c_j, 2) \neq s(c_j, 2)$, create a replica r^j , such that $r^j(c_j, 2) = \bar{s}(c_j, 2)$.
6. Repeat steps (4-5) to next $t + 1$. The LE $\lambda(t)$ of LCG can be defined as:

$$\lambda(t) = \frac{1}{t} \log \left(\frac{\sum_{r^j} \sum_{c_i} h(c_i, t)}{\sum_{c_i} h(c_i, 0)} \right) \quad (1)$$

Results and discussions

The study showed that LE could be effectively using as a measure of PRNG randomness, since the theoretical LE for LCG ($\lambda \approx \log A$) would

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Figure 1: Comparison of LE curves. We used 5 dataset composed by different A, B and C parameters, consisting of Mersenne's primes ($M_p = 2^p - 1$) sampled with 100 seeds (Y_0) randomly chosen. Figure 1 shows that Data 1-2 got declining curves with higher LE, while the others curves got 0, which means non-chaotic behavior.

not show sensitivity of parameters (A, B, C). Results confirm that prime numbers are better than non-prime. Perhaps, there is still a lack of normalization and further tests are necessary.

References

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